

ISic0272

I.Sicily inscription 0272

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Dis Manib(us) □
2. □ Epilanta
3. □no □ Patra □
4. Annius □ Chry
5. santa · alumn[o]
6. □ b(ene) · m(erenti) ·

Apparatus

Text based upon Bitto 2001

Translation (en)

To the shades of the underworld, for Epilantanus Patra. Annius Chrysanta (set this up) for his well-deserved pupil.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284769

EDR 033609

EDCS 21900302

PHI 313703

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.6983 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At xxi

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